

COURSE OF BREAST CANCER IN PATIENTS, WHO HAVE HAD A CORONAVIRUS INFECTION .

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Abstract. The article discusses the course of breast cancer in patients, who have had coronavirus infection. The effect of coronavirus infection on the treatment of cancer patients was analyzed. Cancer patients are the most vulnerable group, as they are at increased risk of immunosuppression, the elderly, and the presence of concomitant (diabetes, cardiovascular) diseases. The manifestation of the post-covid syndrome, which requires further study, is becoming relevant.

Keywords. Covid-19 pandemic, post-covid syndrome, breast cancer (BC), radical mastectomy (RME), acute respiratory infections.

Purpose of the study: To assess the clinical picture, course, and specific treatment of breast cancer in patients with a history of coronavirus infection.

Research objectives:

1. To study the features of the course of breast cancer in patients who have had a coronavirus infection.

2. Develop chemotherapy courses for patients with breast cancer, taking into account the past Covid-19.

Relevance: Most of the population of the Andijan region of the Republic of Uzbekistan became infected with Covid-19 infection due to the epidemic. The analysis of infectivity and the course of pathology largely depended on the body's immune defenses.

Cancer patients are a special group because their treatment cannot be terminated.

The global healthcare system is faced with an atypical situation that requires, on the one hand, an urgent revision of the standards for treating cancer patients, and, on the other hand, maintaining the quality of care provided. The available experience is extremely small, heterogeneous and, in most cases, is based on single observations. Therefore, it is relevant to organize care for patients in a pandemic, as well as to find an answer to the question of how coronavirus infection affects the prognosis.

In the city of Wuhan, Hubei Province in China, on December 31, 2019, 27 cases of pneumonia of unknown etiology were detected. Causing in patients "Acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus - 2" (SARSCoV-2). This disease has been named COVID-19 by the World Health Organization (WHO). This respiratory virus is highly contagious and can be easily transmitted to other people at a distance of less than 2 meters. The incubation period of the disease is about 14 days, with an average of 6–7 days.

Cancer patients are at higher risk of contracting COVID-19 and have a higher likelihood of morbidity and mortality than the general population. Thus, in a study by Yu J., Ouyang W. (2020), which included a total of 1524 patients with cancer, the risk of developing COVID-19 was twice as high compared to the general population.

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The Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention has described the epidemiological characteristics of 72,314 cases of COVID-19. It was reported that 107 patients (0.5%) had cancer of various locations, and 6 of them died. Mortality was 5.6%, which is higher than the total registered mortality (2.3%).

Oncological patients are at risk of severe course of coronavirus infection COVID-19 due to suppressed immunity against the background of anticancer treatment,

regardless of the duration . According to the WHO, mortality in the group of cancer patients with confirmed coronavirus infection is 7.6%.

For comparison, mortality among other groups with confirmed coronavirus infection is: among patients with cardiovascular diseases- 13.2%, with diabetes mellitus - 9.2%, with arterial hypertension - 8.4%, with chronic respiratory diseases - 8.0% .

Four months after COVID-19, impairment of at least one physiological function—determined clinically, laboratory, or radiographically—occurs in nearly 70% of patients. A year later, at least one manifestation of post-COVID syndrome can be found in about half of the people who were hospitalized for this infection. Changes from various systems and organs are described.

Materials and methods of research.

Observations and detailed analysis of medical records of 124 patients with breast cancer (BC) (of which 19 patients had Covid-19 infection and 105 patients had not had coronavirus infection) were carried out in the mammological department of the Andijan Branch of the Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2021. As a result of the work carried out, 2 groups of observables were formed.

I (explored) observation group - 19 patients who received anticoronavirus therapy against the background of breast cancer.

II (control) group - 105 patients who received hospital treatment for breast cancer without coronavirus infection.

When evaluating the effectiveness of the treatment, the general condition of the patients, the reduction of the breast tumor, the state of the peripheral blood, the state of the biochemical parameters of the blood, and the examination of throat swabs to detect Covid-19 viruses were taken into account.

Age of patients:

№	Age of patients	I group	II group
1	35-40	2 (10,9%)	12 (11,4%)
2	41-50	5 (26%)	31 (29,5%)
3	51-60	10 (53%)	42 (40%)
4	61-70	2 (10,5)	20(19%)
	In all	19	105

Factors affecting the course of anticancer therapy in cancer patients are the stage and presence of an active tumor process, as well as the age of patients. Among the observed in both groups, patients aged 51-60 years prevailed (10 (53%) in group I and 42 (40%) in group II). 5 patients were diagnosed with comorbidities, such as arterial hypertension, who were prescribed antihypertensive drugs.

After optimizing blood pressure, specific treatment continued, such as chemotherapy, hormone therapy, and others. In 3 patients, the disease was complicated by pleuropneumonia with accumulation of fluid in the pleural cavity. Specific treatment was stopped and patients were transferred for treatment of complications of coronavirus infection. In 6 patients, acute respiratory infections of the upper respiratory tract were detected, which, after repeated testing for Covid-19, received specific treatment.

In 4 patients, after treatment for coronavirus infection, the condition allowed the continuation of specific treatment. On the 4th day after RME, one patient developed a Covid-19 infection clinic, which was transferred to a specialized medical center for the treatment of coronavirus infection.

All the observed patients underwent a clinical minimum of examinations and the necessary to verify the diagnosis of Covid-19 infection in cancer patients.

The clinical manifestations of the disease were assessed and therapeutic and diagnostic measures were taken.

With each patient who recovered from coronavirus infection, an explanatory conversation was held about the epidemic danger of the disease, the need for precautionary measures and nutritional value.

Results and conclusions.

An analysis of the clinical manifestations of patients who had a coronavirus infection showed the presence of malaise, a feeling of lack of air, an intermittent cough, and a change in appetite. In the clinical analysis of blood, no significant deviations were noted in the predominant number of patients, but in some individuals one can see moderate leukopenia in group I compared to group II.

The continuation of specific treatment was carried out according to the standard, depending on the stage of the process. Complaints about poor tolerance of chemotherapy were presented by 4 (21%) patients of group I and 10 (9.5%) patients of group II. However, after a short-term discontinuation of drugs and hydration of the body, complaints were stopped in all patients.

A comparison of one-year relapse-free survival showed that 13 (68.4%) patients with coronavirus infection had the appearance of distant metastases and a noticeable increase in the primary tumor (most likely due to a violation of the rhythm of chemotherapy) compared with the second group, where it was noted in 18 (17.1%) of patients.

Thus, the peculiarity of the course of breast cancer in patients with Covid-19 infection was revealed, as evidenced by complications such as: pleuropneumonia, decreased immunity, a sharp weakening of the body; which leads to the suspension of specific treatment, which is covered by complications such as tumor recurrence and the appearance of new metastases.

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